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FUNCTIONAL ECOLOGY OF MEDITERRANEAN LIZARDS HAS CONSERVATION IMPLICATIONS

SUMMARY

In a context of biodiversity loss, conservation can no longer rely on identifying patterns but should also uncover the subjacent processes. As such, the functional responses of organisms to disturbance need to be recognised, quantified and, if possible, managed. I illustrate this by focusing on lizards, a pivotal element in Mediterranean terrestrial networks linking invertebrates to endotherm vertebrates. Their importance is accentuated in southern areas and in islands, where climate is less restrictive and trophic resources fluctuate abruptly. Under these conditions, ectotherm way of life becomes advantageous due to low maintenances, but also carries substantial costs associated to activity and habitat restrictions and exposure to water loss, radiation, predators, parasites, and competitors. Balance between these forces may be attained at different optima depending on the species or intraspecific class. The complex biogeography of the Mediterranean provides multiple opportunities for species overlap. Community assemblage tends to be based on niche conservatism and overlap opportunity, but niche shift and character displacement are also documented. Environmental context is decisive to determine local community dynamics. The degree of flexibility in biological functions greatly vary across species either due to selection or to phenotypic plasticity. Species displaying lower variation tend to be spatially restricted. Resilience to disturbance also relies on such flexibility with specialists becoming more threatened. Some species consist of alternative morphs, which provide faster response to changing environments. Nevertheless, disturbance factors (climate change, habitat degradation, invasive species) and biological responses (life history, thermoregulation and hydroregulation) are interactive. In a Mediterranean Basin where pristine environments are becoming an exception, this complex reality cannot be ignored to implement effective conservation strategies.

Key words: Biodiversity, lacertids, trophic networks, ecophysiology, adaptation, phenotypic plasticity, global change, pollution, bioinvasions.

RIASSUNTO

L'ecologia funzionale delle lucertole mediterranee ha implicazioni conservazionistiche. In un contesto di perdita della biodiversità, la conservazione non può più basarsi sull'identificazione di

modelli ma dovrebbe anche scoprire i processi sottostanti. Pertanto le risposte funzionali degli organismi al disturbo devono essere riconosciute, quantificate e, se possibile, gestite. Illustrerò questo concentrandomi sulle lucertole, un elemento cardine nelle reti trofiche mediterranee che collegano gli invertebrati ai vertebrati endotermi. La loro importanza è accentuata nelle aree meridionali e nelle isole dove il clima è meno limitante e le risorse trofiche subiscono forti fluttuazioni. In queste condizioni lo stile di vita ectotermo diventa vantaggioso a causa del basso costo di mantenimento, ma comporta anche costi sostanziali associati all'attività ed alle restrizioni dell'habitat e all'esposizione alla perdita di acqua, radiazione, predatori, parassiti e competitori. L'equilibrio tra queste forze può essere raggiunto a livelli ottimali diversi a seconda delle specie o della classe intraspecifica. La complessa biogeografia del Mediterraneo provvede diverse opportunità per la sovrapposizione tra specie. L'assemblaggio della comunità tende ad essere basato sulla conservazione della nicchia e le opportunità di sovrapposizione, ma sono anche documentati cambiamenti di nicchia e spostamenti di carattere. Il contesto ambientale è decisivo per determinare le dinamiche della comunità locale. Il grado di flessibilità nelle funzioni biologiche varia notevolmente tra le specie sia a causa della selezione sia a causa della plasticità fenotipica. Le specie che mostrano variazioni minori tendono ad essere limitate nello spazio. La resilienza al disturbo si basa anche su tale flessibilità, ove le specie specialiste divengono più minacciate. Alcune specie si presentano con 'morfi' alternativi, che rispondono più velocemente agli ambienti che cambiano. Tuttavia, i fattori di disturbo (cambiamenti climatici, degrado dell'habitat, specie invasive) e le risposte biologiche (storia della vita, termoregolazione e idroregolazione) sono interattivi. Nel bacino del Mediterraneo, dove gli ambienti incontaminati stanno diventando un'eccezione, questa complessa realtà non può essere ignorata per attuare efficaci strategie di conservazione.

Parole chiave: Biodiversità, lacertidi, reti trofiche, ecofisiologia, adattamento, plasticità fenotipica, cambiamento globale, inquinamento, invasioni biologiche.

The attributes of biodiversity, composition, structure, and function are non-redundant but complementary, that is, they cannot be simply deduced one from another (NOSS, 1990). In a planetary context of biodiversity loss, conservation policies can no longer rely exclusively on identifying spatio-temporal patterns of biodiversity (Fig. 1), but should also uncover the subjacent processes generating, maintaining, and destroying it. As such, the functional responses of organisms to disturbance factors, either abiotic or biotic, need to be recognised, quantified and, if possible, anticipated and minimised (KEARNEY *et al.*, 2021).

Here, I illustrate this approach by focusing on lizards, which constitute pivotal elements in Mediterranean terrestrial networks linking invertebrates to endotherm vertebrates (CARRETERO, 2004). Their importance is even accentuated in southern areas and in islands, where climate is less restrictive and trophic resources suffer abrupt fluctuations (PÉREZ-MELLADO & CORTI, 1993, Fig. 2). Under these conditions, ectotherm way of life becomes advantageous in terms of low maintenance costs, but also carries substantial costs associated to activity and habitat restrictions and exposure to water loss (SANNOLO & CARRETERO, 2019), UV radiation (REGUERA *et al.*, 2014), predators (ŽAGAR *et al.*, 2015), parasites (MEGÍA-PALMA *et al.*, 2020) and competitors (ŽAGAR *et al.*,

Fig. 1 — The usual correlative approach to the study of biodiversity. Environmental factors and biological responses are associated on the basis of spatial and temporal coincidence to infer trends, design management measures and to ensure their effectiveness. Organisms are considered as a black box neglecting the internal causative mechanisms. This may produce unexpected outcomes and incorrect management decisions.

2015, 2017). Balance between these, often conflicting, forces may be attained at different optima depending on the species and even the population, sex, stage, and season (BRAÑA & JI, 2000; CARRETERO *et al*, 2005; SANNOLO *et al*, 2018, 2019; FERNÁNDEZ-RODRÍGUEZ *et al*, 2021, among others).

However, we still lack solid evidence of the temporal and spatial extent of top and down regulation of Mediterranean lizard populations inhabiting natural and modified ecosystems (e.g., agro-environments). This not only hinders our efforts for inferring population trends but also precludes our interpretations on the demographic responses to environmental changes and disturbance. While some biological responses, such herbivory in insular systems, are well documented (VAN DAMME, 1999), experimental evidence on lizard community dynamics is still in the cradle (PRINGLE *et al*, 2019). The recent snake invasions in some island systems, beyond the dramatic ecological catastrophe for the native species affected (CABRERA-PÉREZ *et al*, 2012; MONTES *et al*, 2021), may also represent the chance to understand their role in insular systems.

The complex biogeographical history of the Mediterranean provides

Fig. 2 — Schematic representation of lizard trophic networks in typical continental and insular systems. In the first, lizard populations tend to be top regulated but predation pressure and only occasionally limited by prey availability. In the second, diminished predation pressure allows high lizard densities with strong intraspecific competition, approaching carrying capacity during substantial parts of the year, which hence become down regulated (after CARRETERO, 2004, modified).

multiple opportunities for species overlap at geographic and ecological level (BLONDEL *et al.*, 2010). Community assemblage tends to be based on niche conservatism (GARCIA-PORTA *et al.*, 2020) and overlap opportunity (ARNOLD, 1987), but niche shift and character displacement are also documented, especially among congeneric species (CARRETERO, 2008). In all cases, the environmental context is decisive to determine local community structure and dynamics. The degree of flexibility in biological functions greatly vary across species either due to selection on particular traits or to phenotypic plasticity (KALIONTZOPOULOU *et al.*, 2010b). Species displaying lower variation tend to be restricted in habitat and range (KALIONTZOPOULOU *et al.*, 2010a). Resilience to disturbance also seems to rely on such flexibility with specialists becoming more threatened than generalists (AMARAL 2012a, 2012b; LAZI *et al.*, 2015; SIMBULA 2021a, 2021b). Remarkably, some species consist of alternative morphs varying in frequency, which provide faster response to changing environments (PÉREZ I DE LANUZA, 2018a, 2018b). Nevertheless, disturbance factors (climate change, pollution, habitat degradation, invasive

species) and biological responses (life history, thermoregulation and hydroregulation) are interactive (see for instance FERREIRA *et al.*, 2015; SANNOLO *et al.*, 2018; DAMAS-MOREIRA *et al.*, 2020). In a Mediterranean Basin where pristine environments are becoming an exception, this complex reality cannot be ignored if we wish to design effective conservation strategies (see a proposal for such approach in Fig. 3).

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Fig. 3 — A proposal for a functional approach to conservation of Mediterranean lizards. The biological response of species towards environmental conditions (including disturbance) will depend on the exposure (degree of coincidence in time and species), on the performance of biological functions with such factors, on the variation of species and populations and on the previous history of biological interaction. These four pathways will be traded-off not only at level population and species but also at the level of communities and ecosystems.

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